

APPLICATION OF MCDM METHODS FOR SELECTION OF WEDM PROCESS PARAMETERS FOR ALUMINUM METAL MATRIX

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ABSTRACT

Due to new enlargement and demand of the mechanical industry for machining of composite materials which having high hardness, toughness and impact resistance, such metals are not easily machined by conventional machining methods. For that, advance machining methods such as EDM, WEDM, ECM, USM, etc introduced. Conductive ceramics, steel, aerospace and automobile materials are easily machined by WEDM process. Study has been made on effect of different aluminium metal matrix material, wire electrode material, wire diameter, pulse on time and pulse off time on WEDM performance material removal rate surface roughness and cutting velocity. Mix level taguchi L_{96} orthogonal array used for experiment and MCDM optimization method like gray relational analysis method applied to responses considering different weightage criteria for finding out the optimum parameter sets. It was found that optimum parameter set Workpiece Material: Al+SiC, Wire Type: Coated, T_{on} : 130 μ s, T_{off} : 54 μ s, D_w : 0.3mm.

KEYWORDS: Wire electrical discharge machining process, Gray relational analysis, MCDM methods.

1. INTRODUCTION

Wire electrical discharge machining (WEDM) is a non-traditional machining process that uses electricity to cut any conductive material precisely and accurately, electrically charged copper or brass wire uses as an electrode. During the wire EDM process, wire carries one side of an electrical charge and work piece carries other side of the charge. When the wire gets close to the part, the attraction of electrical charges creates a controlled spark, melting and vaporizing microscopic particles of material. The spark also removes a minuscule chunk of the wire, so after the wire travels through the work piece one time, the machine discards the used wire and automatically advances new wire. Peter et al. (2014) use gray relational analysis methods to find out optimum process parameter of WEDM process. In this A413 aluminium alloy reinforced with 20 microns of boron carbide and 75 microns of fly ash, hybrid composites was fabricated using stir casting technique. Experimental results show that parameter gap voltage has the most significant effect on the multiple performance characteristics. Factor pulse on time is second and is followed by factors wire feed, reinforcement and pulse off time. Varun and Venkaiah (2015) a new optimization strategy by coupling grey relational analysis with genetic algorithm is proposed to simultaneously optimize the response parameters. Experiments were conducted on EN353 work material to study the effects of various process parameters on the response parameter such as material removal rate, surface roughness and cutting width. Process parameters such as pulse on time, pulse off time, peak current, and servo voltage are considered. ANOVA analysis was carried out to find the parameters affecting the responses with the help of 3D surface plots. Kumar and Kumar (2018) study effects of WEDM characteristics on MRR, SR and WWR in machining of Inconel 825 superalloy. It was found that T_{on} , W_F , T_{off} , IP most contributing factor for MRR, SR, and WWR followed by SV and W_T . Multi response optimization

resulted in 13.62% improvement in MRR whereas SR and WWR were reduced by 13.97 % and 4.03% respectively. Pujara et al. (2018) describes an investigation on the optimization of process parameters on the material

removal rate and kerf in wire electrical discharge machining operations. Experiments were carried out under varying pulse ON/OFF time, peak current, and wire feed by using Taguchi L_9 orthogonal array. Grey relational analysis optimization technique is used to find the optimal selection of process parameters for improvement in WEDM performance. Kumar and D.S. (2019) examined the performance parameters of WEDM to improve the productivity and material removal rate (MRR) with a high surface finish of high chromium-high carbon die steel. WEDM process parameters for D₃ die steel had optimized by using Grey relational analysis method coupled with Taguchi method. The optimum solution has been calculated for MRR, cutting speed, machining time and surface roughness. A fuzzy logic model using Matlab was developed for the prediction of performance parameters, namely MRR, cutting speed (Cs), machining time (M/c time) and SR with respect to changes in input parameters. Patel and Maniya (2019) has been carried out experiments on WEDM process considering uncoated three different wire material as electrode and three different AMC materials use as workpiece material. It was found that brass wire with 0.25 mm and 0.3 mm wire diameter is most effective for WEDM selected responses.

Novelty of this paper to develop semi-empirical model taking into consideration of wire diameter, pulse on time, peak current as process parameters and material properties. Study was describing the material removal rate of WEDM of aluminum metal matrix, using three different wire electrodes with different diameter. Copper, Brass, Molybdenum of 0.2, 0.25, 0.3 mm diameter wire were utilized in the conducted research.

Novelty of this paper to study effects various aluminium matrix material, wire electrode material, wire diameter and electrical parameter like pulse on time and pulse off time on machining performance reported. Many experimental studies have been undertaken on WEDM but studied effects of aluminum matrix composites, wire electrode material and wire diameter less work have been reported. The objective of this study was to find out optimum parameter set for aluminium matrix material, wire electrode material and wire diameter of the commercially employed wire electrodes. WEDM process performance efficiency closely depends on how wire electrode tool relative the machining parameter such as pulse on time, pulse off time, flushing pressure and gap voltage. So wire electrode tool selection based on following objectives: avoid short circuit, high electrical conductivity without breakage, high straightness between two guides, avoid bridging of the gap by severe contamination etc.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The following section highlights the material and its properties, methods of composite preparation, designing for the experimental studies (Patel and Maniya, 2019)

MATERIAL

Aluminium matrix material for present study is Al+SiC, Al+B₄C and Al+ZrO₂. Table 1 gives the chemical composition of Al6061 and Table 2 to Table 4 represents chemical composition of SiC, B₄C and ZrO₂ which is used as reinforcing material of particle sizes 220 mesh (Patel and Maniya, 2019).

Table1:ChemicalCompositionof Al6061 byWt%

Element	Si	Fe	Cu	Mn	Ni	Pb	Zn	Ti	Sn	Mg	Cr	Al
%Wt	0.43	0.7	0.24	0.139	0.05	0.24	0.25	0.15	0.001	0.802	0.25	Balance

Table2: ChemicalCompositionofSiCbyWt%

Element	SiC	Si	SiO ₂	Fe	Al	C
%Wt	98.5	0.3	0.5	0.08	0.1	0.3

Table3: ChemicalcompositionofB₄CbyW_t%

Element	B+C	B	C	B ₂ O ₃	Fe	Si
%W _t	94	74.5	23.5	0.3	0.1	0.1

Table4:Chemical compositionof ZrO₂ byW_t%

Element	Zro ₂	SiO ₂	TiO ₂	Fe ₂ O ₃	Other
%W _t	99.5	0.10	0.007	0.002	0.39

COMPOSITEFABRICATIONPROCESS

Aluminium 6061 grade melted in coal furnace at temperature of 680 °C then the molten metal cooled to its semisolid temperature. Aluminium at semi solid temperature de-moisturized powder of 220 mesh size mixed manuallywith the aluminium. Then mixer again heated to melting temperature of aluminium and mechanical stirring of 3 mincarried out so the particle of de-moisturized powder distributed well. Then the molten mixer poured in the sandmould prepared previously.After solidification of work piece sand removed and the plate of 150mm*150mm*17mmcleaned. Then plate cut so get 25mm*25mm*17mm piece each from it for experiment.Figure 1 show some processof workpiecepreparation (Patel andManiya,2019)..

Figure1: WorkpieceSample

DESIGNING FOR THE EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES

To understanding the behavior of the WEDM process with different wire electrodes having different diameters a systematic plan was made for conducting the experiments. ELPULS-40 DLX WEDM machine used for experiments as shown in Figure 2. Experiments were conducted by using statistically designed Taguchi's L_{16} orthogonal array. The machining process parameters chosen for this study are shown in Table 5 with their levels and ranges of variation of these factors are decided on the basis of some preliminary experiments as well as operator experience and literature survey.

Figure 2: WEDM machine setup

Table 5: Process parameter and their level

Factor	Level1	Level2	Level3	Level4
Workpiece Material	Al+SiC	Al+B ₄ C	Al+ZrO ₂	--
Wire Type	Uncoated Brass	Zincoated Brass	--	--
Wire diameter (d_w , mm)	0.25	0.3	--	--
Pulse on time (T_{on} , μ s)	108	115	123	130
Pulse off time (T_{off} , μ s)	50	54	58	62

The responses to measure the performance of the process were material removal rate, surface roughness and cutting velocity. Material removal rate can be found by using the equation 1 where weight of work piece measure by weight measurement machine as shown in Figure 3. Surface roughness was measured by using Mitutoyo surface roughness tester as shown in Figure 4 in terms of CLA values (R_a) having stroke length 0.8 cm and speed of probe of tester fixed 0.5 mm/sec. Cutting velocity was found by using the equation 2 where as cutting length is measured by vernier caliper. Table 6 represents the process parameters and results of output parameter of WEDM machine.

$$MRR = \frac{W_b - W_a}{\rho \times T} \quad (1)$$

Where,

W_b = Weight before experiment

W_a =WeightbeforeexperimentT

=Time takentocut.

ρ =Densityofmaterial

$$\text{CuttingVelocity} = \frac{\text{CuttingLengthofWorkpiece}}{\text{TimetoCut}} \quad (2)$$

Figure3:WeightMeasurementMachine

Figure4:SurfaceRoughnessTester

Table6:Processparameter andresult

Sr. No.	WorkPiece	WireMaterial	T _{on} (μ s)	T _{off} (μ s)	D _w (mm)	MRR (mm ³ /min)	SR (μ m)	CV (mm /min)
1	Al+SiC	Uncoated	108	50	0.25	13.52	3.275	2.94
2	Al+SiC	Uncoated	108	54	0.25	10.78	2.921	2.35
3	Al+SiC	Uncoated	108	58	0.3	9.62	3.030	1.85
4	Al+SiC	Uncoated	108	62	0.3	7.76	2.917	1.66
5	Al+SiC	Uncoated	115	50	0.25	26.87	3.787	4.97
6	Al+SiC	Uncoated	115	54	0.25	23.35	3.247	4.58
7	Al+SiC	Uncoated	115	58	0.3	17.19	3.718	3.34
8	Al+SiC	Uncoated	115	62	0.3	14.94	3.885	2.94

9	Al+SiC	Uncoated	123	50	0.3	30.17	4.302	5.43
10	Al+SiC	Uncoated	123	54	0.3	26.40	4.423	4.74
11	Al+SiC	Uncoated	123	58	0.25	32.37	4.092	5.74
12	Al+SiC	Uncoated	123	62	0.25	26.76	4.032	4.97
13	Al+SiC	Uncoated	130	50	0.3	30.43	4.161	5.56
14	Al+SiC	Uncoated	130	54	0.3	25.71	3.853	4.70
15	Al+SiC	Uncoated	130	58	0.25	30.56	4.558	5.75
16	Al+SiC	Uncoated	130	62	0.25	27.25	4.516	4.98
17	Al+SiC	Coated	108	50	0.25	15.02	3.330	3.27
18	Al+SiC	Coated	108	54	0.25	12.30	3.207	2.75
19	Al+SiC	Coated	108	58	0.3	10.49	3.431	1.98
20	Al+SiC	Coated	108	62	0.3	9.40	3.375	1.75
21	Al+SiC	Coated	115	50	0.25	35.83	3.721	6.99
22	Al+SiC	Coated	115	54	0.25	28.49	4.024	5.53
23	Al+SiC	Coated	115	58	0.3	23.83	4.221	4.12
24	Al+SiC	Coated	115	62	0.3	21.61	3.805	3.71
25	Al+SiC	Coated	123	50	0.3	48.53	4.115	7.77
26	Al+SiC	Coated	123	54	0.3	47.51	4.372	7.50
27	Al+SiC	Coated	123	58	0.25	39.16	4.586	7.19
28	Al+SiC	Coated	123	62	0.25	33.37	4.818	6.03
29	Al+SiC	Coated	130	50	0.3	56.18	4.322	9.08
30	Al+SiC	Coated	130	54	0.3	46.52	4.980	7.39
31	Al+SiC	Coated	130	58	0.25	39.37	4.800	7.34

32	Al+SiC	Coated	130	62	0.25	33.39	4.328	6.07
33	Al+B ₄ C	Uncoated	108	50	0.25	14.59	2.870	2.98
34	Al+B ₄ C	Uncoated	108	54	0.25	11.97	2.987	2.48
35	Al+B ₄ C	Uncoated	108	58	0.3	8.54	3.393	1.75
36	Al+B ₄ C	Uncoated	108	62	0.3	8.28	3.183	1.64
37	Al+B ₄ C	Uncoated	115	50	0.25	30.57	3.949	5.69
38	Al+B ₄ C	Uncoated	115	54	0.25	24.65	3.653	4.70
39	Al+B ₄ C	Uncoated	115	58	0.3	17.31	4.122	3.40
40	Al+B ₄ C	Uncoated	115	62	0.3	15.70	3.640	3.04
41	Al+B ₄ C	Uncoated	123	50	0.3	29.09	4.135	4.92
42	Al+B ₄ C	Uncoated	123	54	0.3	26.12	4.866	5.31
43	Al+B ₄ C	Uncoated	123	58	0.25	33.53	4.153	5.81
44	Al+B ₄ C	Uncoated	123	62	0.25	29.28	4.783	5.65
45	Al+B ₄ C	Uncoated	130	50	0.3	29.17	4.256	4.99
46	Al+B ₄ C	Uncoated	130	54	0.3	27.52	4.347	4.66
47	Al+B ₄ C	Uncoated	130	58	0.25	34.78	4.225	5.93
48	Al+B ₄ C	Uncoated	130	62	0.25	30.47	4.427	5.34
49	Al+B ₄ C	Coated	108	50	0.25	19.48	3.470	3.81
50	Al+B ₄ C	Coated	108	54	0.25	15.66	3.299	3.11
51	Al+B ₄ C	Coated	108	58	0.3	11.65	3.194	2.03
52	Al+B ₄ C	Coated	108	62	0.3	10.06	3.328	1.81
53	Al+B ₄ C	Coated	115	50	0.25	41.49	4.155	7.31
54	Al+B ₄ C	Coated	115	54	0.25	34.06	3.826	6.07

55	Al+B ₄ C	Coated	115	58	0.3	27.29	3.875	4.34
56	Al+B ₄ C	Coated	115	62	0.3	23.10	4.697	3.78
57	Al+B ₄ C	Coated	123	50	0.3	53.70	4.554	7.97
58	Al+B ₄ C	Coated	123	54	0.3	48.95	4.152	7.43
59	Al+B ₄ C	Coated	123	58	0.25	44.39	4.751	7.40
60	Al+B ₄ C	Coated	123	62	0.25	40.16	4.830	7.05
61	Al+B ₄ C	Coated	130	50	0.3	54.41	4.808	8.05
62	Al+B ₄ C	Coated	130	54	0.3	48.52	4.672	7.28
63	Al+B ₄ C	Coated	130	58	0.25	44.87	4.756	7.60
64	Al+B ₄ C	Coated	130	62	0.25	41.02	4.502	6.91
65	Al+ZrO ₂	Uncoated	108	50	0.25	14.80	2.884	3.23
66	Al+ZrO ₂	Uncoated	108	54	0.25	11.18	3.612	2.64
67	Al+ZrO ₂	Uncoated	108	58	0.3	8.61	3.243	1.87
68	Al+ZrO ₂	Uncoated	108	62	0.3	7.32	3.049	1.60
69	Al+ZrO ₂	Uncoated	115	50	0.25	29.21	4.413	6.77
70	Al+ZrO ₂	Uncoated	115	54	0.25	23.68	3.886	4.85
71	Al+ZrO ₂	Uncoated	115	58	0.3	16.53	3.778	3.33
72	Al+ZrO ₂	Uncoated	115	62	0.3	14.33	3.596	2.90
73	Al+ZrO ₂	Uncoated	123	50	0.3	28.66	3.987	5.32
74	Al+ZrO ₂	Uncoated	123	54	0.3	25.07	4.367	4.69
75	Al+ZrO ₂	Uncoated	123	58	0.25	31.78	4.348	5.98
76	Al+ZrO ₂	Uncoated	123	62	0.25	28.77	4.982	5.45
77	Al+ZrO ₂	Uncoated	130	50	0.3	30.60	4.685	5.53

78	Al+ZrO ₂	Uncoated	130	54	0.3	26.091	3.802	4.88
79	Al+ZrO ₂	Uncoated	130	58	0.25	31.66	4.632	5.96
80	Al+ZrO ₂	Uncoated	130	62	0.25	14.95	4.889	5.66
81	Al+ZrO ₂	Coated	108	50	0.25	19.22	3.489	4.23
82	Al+ZrO ₂	Coated	108	54	0.25	15.33	4.068	3.23
83	Al+ZrO ₂	Coated	108	58	0.3	11.14	3.273	2.14
84	Al+ZrO ₂	Coated	108	62	0.3	9.49	3.085	1.82
85	Al+ZrO ₂	Coated	115	50	0.25	37.95	4.004	7.31
86	Al+ZrO ₂	Coated	115	54	0.25	19.53	3.584	6.09
87	Al+ZrO ₂	Coated	115	58	0.3	26.14	3.602	4.53
88	Al+ZrO ₂	Coated	115	62	0.3	22.17	4.228	3.91
89	Al+ZrO ₂	Coated	123	50	0.3	48.53	4.940	7.92
90	Al+ZrO ₂	Coated	123	54	0.3	44.60	4.335	7.43
91	Al+ZrO ₂	Coated	123	58	0.25	41.30	4.446	7.46
92	Al+ZrO ₂	Coated	123	62	0.25	37.80	4.040	7.00
93	Al+ZrO ₂	Coated	130	50	0.3	52.42	4.356	8.28
94	Al+ZrO ₂	Coated	130	54	0.3	45.72	4.525	7.54
95	Al+ZrO ₂	Coated	130	58	0.25	42.21	4.684	7.53
96	Al+ZrO ₂	Coated	130	62	0.25	38.56	4.717	6.99

3. MCDMMETHODS

Multi criteria decision making methods is best tool for the decision maker when selection of best alternative or valueamong of the value or alternative as per the decided goal and objective. Figure 5 shows the step of multi criteriadecision makingmethods.

Figure 5: Process step of multicriteria decision making method

MCDM refers creating decisions in the presence of various, typically conflicting criteria. Depending on whether the problem is a selection problem or a design problem, the problems of MCDM can be generally categorized into two

(1) Multiple Attribute Decision Making (MADM) and (2) Multiple Objective Decisions Making (MODM). When infinite or a large number of choices are present among which solution is suitable for the decision maker for that MODM method is used. Genetic algorithm, particle swarm optimization, ant colony optimization, teaching learning based optimization, ant bee colony etc are MODM methods. When finite number or limited number of alternatives available among which solution is suitable for decision maker for that MADM methods use. AHP, PROMOTHEE, TOPSIS, MOORA, ARAS, OCRA, GRA etc are MADM methods.

GRAY RELATIONAL ANALYSIS METHOD

GRA methods provides all the information by representing the information in color coding form in this methods black color represent no information and white color represents its having all information (Deng, 1989). Benefits of GRA methods applied to 96 experiments is when experiments not perform in proper form at that time GRA

gives better statistical regression also calculation of GRA methods is simple and take less time as compare to other MCDM methods. In GRA methods first data is normalized and then coefficient of gray relation was found. On basis of coefficient gray relational grade is found and then ranking of alternative given the alternative which having highest value of gray relational grade they can receive first rank. Step and illustration of GRA methods listed as below. 96 experimental runs are listed in Table 6 for optimal response of WEDM process parameter such as MRR, CV and SR. It is concerned the higher MRR, CV and lower SR are indications of better performance.

Step: 1 Data Normalization.

If the target value of original sequence is infinite, then it has a characteristic of "the larger the better". The original sequence can be normalized as follows:

$$X_i(k) = \frac{Y_i(k) - \min_{i(k)}}{Y_i(k) \max_{i(k)} - \min_{i(k)}} \quad (3)$$

If the expectancy is "the smaller the better" than the original sequence should be normalized as follows:

$$Xi(k) = \frac{\max Yi(k)}{-Yi(k)\max Yi(k) - \min Yi(k)} \quad (4)$$

Here $X(k)_i$ is the value after grey relational generation, $\min Y(k)_i$ is the smallest value of $Y(k)_i$ for the k^{th} response, and $\max Y(k)_i$ is the largest value of $Y(k)_i$ for the k^{th} response. Normalized data as shown in Table 7 in which MRR and CV can be considered as beneficial attributes and SR can be considered as non-beneficial attributes.

Table 7: Normalized decision matrix

Sr. No.	MRR (mm ³ /min)	SR (μm)	CV (mm/min)
1	0.12690	0.80824	0.17936
2	0.07073	0.97585	0.10076
3	0.04707	0.92424	0.03413
4	0.00885	0.97775	0.00826
5	0.40002	0.56581	0.45007
6	0.32797	0.82150	0.39918
7	0.20194	0.59849	0.23304
8	0.15584	0.51941	0.17872
9	0.46754	0.32197	0.51269
10	0.39035	0.26468	0.42011
11	0.51258	0.4214	0.55314
12	0.39784	0.44981	0.45008
13	0.47282	0.38873	0.52964
14	0.37626	0.53456	0.41412
15	0.4756	0.20076	0.55473
16	0.40791	0.22064	0.45140
17	0.15756	0.78220	0.22297

18	0.1019	0.84044	0.15344
19	0.06491	0.73438	0.05031
20	0.04245	0.76089	0.02035
21	0.58351	0.59706	0.72068
22	0.43322	0.45360	0.52604
23	0.33789	0.36032	0.33660
24	0.29245	0.55729	0.28234
25	0.84344	0.41051	0.82447
26	0.82256	0.28883	0.78828
27	0.65152	0.18750	0.74785
28	0.53316	0.07765	0.59235
29	1.00000	0.3125	1.00000
30	0.80214	0.00095	0.77443
31	0.65595	0.08617	0.76765
32	0.53354	0.30966	0.59810
33	0.14878	1.00000	0.18503
34	0.09507	0.9446	0.11729
35	0.02491	0.75237	0.02048
36	0.01955	0.8518	0.00611
37	0.47575	0.48911	0.54642
38	0.35453	0.62926	0.41412
39	0.20441	0.4072	0.24123
40	0.17155	0.63542	0.19227

41	0.44546	0.40104	0.44336
42	0.38473	0.05492	0.49620
43	0.53633	0.39252	0.56332
44	0.44931	0.09422	0.54151
45	0.44712	0.34375	0.45273
46	0.4133	0.30066	0.40862
47	0.56204	0.35843	0.57968
48	0.47382	0.26278	0.50083
49	0.24884	0.71591	0.29551
50	0.17061	0.79688	0.20215
51	0.08866	0.84659	0.05773
52	0.05605	0.78314	0.02868
53	0.6992	0.39157	0.76420
54	0.54718	0.54735	0.59741
55	0.40873	0.52415	0.36686
56	0.32295	0.13494	0.29210
57	0.9492	0.20265	0.85174
58	0.85196	0.39299	0.77992
59	0.75870	0.10938	0.77515
60	0.67195	0.07197	0.72813
61	0.9636	0.08239	0.86218
62	0.84316	0.14678	0.75908
63	0.76843	0.10701	0.80164

64	0.68974	0.22727	0.70997
65	0.15299	0.99337	0.2187
66	0.07886	0.64867	0.13885
67	0.02626	0.82339	0.03576
68	0.00000	0.91525	0.00000
69	0.44788	0.26941	0.69099
70	0.33467	0.51894	0.43412
71	0.18835	0.57008	0.23123
72	0.14331	0.65625	0.17421
73	0.43671	0.47112	0.49802
74	0.36324	0.29119	0.41324
75	0.50064	0.30019	0.58521
76	0.43899	0.00000	0.51481
77	0.47638	0.14063	0.52604
78	0.38402	0.55871	0.43857
79	0.49816	0.16572	0.58259
80	0.15602	0.04403	0.54297
81	0.24349	0.70691	0.35225
82	0.16387	0.43277	0.21781
83	0.07822	0.80919	0.07175
84	0.04444	0.89820	0.02960
85	0.62683	0.46307	0.76362
86	0.24991	0.66193	0.60023

87	0.38516	0.65341	0.39127
88	0.30394	0.35701	0.30856
89	0.84335	0.01989	0.84471
90	0.76282	0.30635	0.77940
91	0.69547	0.25379	0.78420
92	0.62366	0.44602	0.72221
93	0.92306	0.2964	0.89382
94	0.78576	0.21638	0.79459
95	0.71402	0.14110	0.79342
96	0.63938	0.12547	0.72066

Step:2GreyRelationalCoefficient.

Follow data Normalization, a grey relational coefficient is calculate to express the relationship between the ideal and actual normalized experimental results. The Grey relation coefficient can be express as follows.

$$\zeta_i(k) = \frac{\Delta_{\min} + \psi \Delta_{\max}}{\Delta_i(k) + \psi \Delta_{\max}} \tag{5}$$

Where $\Delta_{0_i}^{(k)}$ is the deviation sequence of the reference sequence $X_0(k)$ and the comparability sequence. ψ = distinguish in or identification coefficient in between zero and one.

$$\Delta_{0_i}(k) = |X_0(k) - X_i(k)| \tag{6}$$

$$\Delta_{\min} = \min_{i \in I} \min_k |X_0(k) - X_i(k)| \tag{7}$$

$$\Delta_{\max} = \max_{i \in I} \max_k |X_0(k) - X_i(k)| \tag{8}$$

Using equation 5 to equation 7 grey relational coefficient can be found by considering identification coefficient value 0.5. Value of identification coefficient Ψ ranges from [0,1] so average value 0.5 taken generally. Grey relational coefficient value is listed in Table 8.

Table8:Greyrelationalcoefficients

Sr. No.	MRR (mm ³ /min)	SR (μm)	CV (mm/min)
1	0.36414	0.72279	0.3786
2	0.34983	0.95393	0.35734
3	0.34413	0.86842	0.3411
4	0.33531	0.95739	0.33518
5	0.45455	0.53523	0.47622
6	0.42661	0.73692	0.45421
7	0.38519	0.55462	0.39464
8	0.37198	0.5099	0.37842
9	0.48428	0.42444	0.50643
10	0.45059	0.40475	0.46301
11	0.50637	0.46357	0.52806
12	0.45365	0.47611	0.47623
13	0.48677	0.44994	0.51527
14	0.44494	0.5179	0.46046
15	0.48809	0.38484	0.52895
16	0.45784	0.39082	0.47683
17	0.37246	0.69657	0.39153
18	0.35763	0.75808	0.37132
19	0.34841	0.65306	0.3449
20	0.34304	0.67649	0.33792

21	0.54556	0.55375	0.64159
22	0.4687	0.47783	0.51337
23	0.43025	0.43872	0.42978
24	0.41406	0.53039	0.41062
25	0.76155	0.45893	0.74015
26	0.73807	0.41282	0.70252
27	0.58929	0.38095	0.66476
28	0.51715	0.35153	0.55088
29	1.00000	0.42105	1.00000
30	0.71647	0.33354	0.68911
31	0.59238	0.35365	0.68273
32	0.51735	0.42005	0.55439
33	0.37004	1.00000	0.38024
34	0.35589	0.90026	0.36161
35	0.33896	0.66878	0.33795
36	0.33774	0.77137	0.3347
37	0.48816	0.49461	0.52434
38	0.4365	0.57423	0.46046
39	0.38593	0.45754	0.39721
40	0.37638	0.57831	0.38234
41	0.47414	0.45498	0.47320
42	0.44832	0.34600	0.49811
43	0.51885	0.45148	0.53380

44	0.47588	0.35568	0.52165
45	0.47489	0.43243	0.47743
46	0.46011	0.4169	0.45814
47	0.53307	0.43799	0.54329
48	0.48725	0.40413	0.50042
49	0.39963	0.63768	0.41511
50	0.37611	0.71111	0.38525
51	0.35427	0.76522	0.34668
52	0.34627	0.69749	0.33983
53	0.62438	0.45109	0.67953
54	0.52476	0.52485	0.55396
55	0.45818	0.51237	0.44125
56	0.42479	0.36629	0.41394
57	0.90776	0.38540	0.77129
58	0.77156	0.45167	0.69437
59	0.67449	0.35955	0.68980
60	0.60383	0.35013	0.64778
61	0.93214	0.35271	0.78392
62	0.76122	0.36949	0.67483
63	0.68346	0.35894	0.71597
64	0.61709	0.39286	0.63289
65	0.37119	0.98692	0.39023
66	0.35183	0.58732	0.36734

67	0.33927	0.73898	0.34148
68	0.33333	0.85506	0.33333
69	0.47523	0.40631	0.61804
70	0.42906	0.50965	0.46910
71	0.3812	0.53768	0.39408
72	0.36854	0.59259	0.37713
73	0.47024	0.48596	0.49901
74	0.43985	0.41363	0.46008
75	0.50032	0.41673	0.54658
76	0.47125	0.33333	0.50752
77	0.48846	0.36782	0.51337
78	0.44804	0.53119	0.47106
79	0.49908	0.37473	0.54502
80	0.37203	0.34342	0.52245
81	0.39793	0.63045	0.43563
82	0.37422	0.4685	0.38996
83	0.35167	0.72378	0.35008
84	0.34351	0.83084	0.34004
85	0.57262	0.48219	0.67900
86	0.39997	0.59661	0.55570
87	0.44849	0.59060	0.45097
88	0.41804	0.43745	0.41966
89	0.76145	0.33781	0.76302

90	0.67826	0.41888	0.69387
91	0.62148	0.40122	0.69852
92	0.57055	0.47439	0.64284
93	0.86664	0.41542	0.82484
94	0.70004	0.38952	0.70880
95	0.63615	0.36794	0.70764
96	0.58097	0.36376	0.64156

Step:3 Grey Relational Grade. After obtaining the Grey relation coefficient, its average is calculated to obtain the Grey relation grade. The Grey relation grade is defined as follows:

$$\gamma_i = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \zeta_i(k) \quad (9)$$

However, since in real application the effect of each factor on the system is not exactly same, Equation 9 can be modified as:

$$\gamma_i = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n W_k \zeta_i(k) \quad (10)$$

Table 9: Grey relational grades

Sr.No.	GRG	Rank
1	0.1627	47
2	0.1844	23
3	0.1725	33
4	0.1807	27
5	0.1627	48
6	0.1796	28
7	0.1481	82

8	0.1399	92
9	0.1571	64
10	0.1463	84
11	0.1663	41
12	0.1561	67
13	0.1612	56
14	0.1580	60
15	0.1556	69
16	0.1471	83
17	0.1621	52
18	0.1651	44
19	0.1494	77
20	0.1507	74
21	0.1932	16
22	0.1620	53
23	0.1442	89
24	0.1504	75
25	0.2176	5
26	0.2057	8
27	0.1815	25
28	0.1576	61
29	0.2687	1
30	0.1930	17

31	0.1808	26
32	0.1656	42
33	0.1943	14
34	0.1796	29
35	0.1494	78
36	0.1603	58
37	0.1673	38
38	0.1633	46
39	0.1377	93
40	0.1484	80
41	0.1557	68
42	0.1435	90
43	0.1670	39
44	0.1502	76
45	0.1537	71
46	0.1482	81
47	0.1681	36
48	0.1545	70
49	0.1612	55
50	0.1634	45
51	0.1627	49
52	0.1536	72
53	0.1948	13

54	0.1780	30
55	0.1567	65
56	0.1338	96
57	0.2292	4
58	0.2129	6
59	0.1913	19
60	0.1778	31
61	0.2296	3
62	0.2004	9
63	0.1952	12
64	0.1824	24
65	0.1941	15
66	0.1450	88
67	0.1576	62
68	0.1689	35
69	0.1665	40
70	0.1563	66
71	0.1457	86
72	0.1485	79
73	0.1615	54
74	0.1458	85
75	0.1625	51
76	0.1456	87

77	0.1520	73
78	0.1610	57
79	0.1575	63
80	0.1374	94
81	0.1625	50
82	0.1368	95
83	0.1582	59
84	0.1681	37
85	0.1925	18
86	0.1723	34
87	0.1654	43
88	0.1415	91
89	0.2067	7
90	0.1988	11
91	0.1911	20
92	0.1873	22
93	0.2339	2
94	0.1996	10
95	0.1900	21
96	0.1761	32

Optimization of result is carried out by using MCDM methods like gray relational analysis methods by considering seven

different weightage criteria for different output parameter

like $C_1: W_1=0.3333, W_2=0.3333, W_3=0.3333; C_2: W_1=0.5, W_2=0.2, W_3=0.3; C_3: W_1=0.3, W_2=0.5, W_3=0.2; C_4:$

$W_1=0.3, W_2=0.5, W_3=0.2; C_5: W_1=0.2, W_2=0.5, W_3=0.3; C_6: W_1=0.3, W_2=0.2, W_3=0.5; C_6: W_1=0.2, W_2=0.3, W_3=0.5.$

5. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

MCDM methods like grey relational analysis methods applied to experimental results considering different weightage criteria for responses like MRR, CV and SR respectively. After optimization process optimum parameter listed in Table 10 for GRA.

Table 10: Optimization result

Sr.No.	Weightage			Optimum input parameter				
	W ₁	W ₂	W ₃	W/P material	Wire type	T _{on}	T _{off}	d _w
1	0.3333	0.3333	0.3333	Al+SiC	Coated	130	54	0.3
2	0.5	0.3	0.2	Al+SiC	Coated	130	54	0.3
3	0.5	0.2	0.3	Al+SiC	Coated	130	54	0.3
4	0.3	0.5	0.2	Al+SiC	Coated	130	54	0.3
5	0.2	0.5	0.3	Al+SiC	Coated	130	54	0.3
6	0.3	0.2	0.5	Al+SiC	Coated	130	54	0.3
7	0.2	0.3	0.5	Al+SiC	Coated	130	54	0.3

From the Table 10 optimum condition is Workpiece material: Al+SiC, Wire material: Coated, Pulse on time: 130 μ s, Pulse off time: 54 μ s, Wire diameter: 0.3mm when experiments perform using Uncoated brass and Zinc coated brass wire use as electrode and three different aluminium matrix material use as workpiece material. Higher value of pulse on time and wire diameter provides higher energy between the working gap of workpiece and electrode. Zinc coated wire material gives better result than uncoated type of wire material due to its higher heat sink effects.

6. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the effects of two types of commercially used wire electrodes were specifically studied experimentally. Finally, it was found that electrical conductivity and percentage of low vapour point temperature zinc on the wire surface were significant on material removal rate, cutting velocity and surface finish. Material removal rate and cutting velocity was improved by performing the experiment by zinc coated brass wire whereas surface roughness increase by performing the experiment uncoated brass wire for all three workpiece material. Also lower the wire diameter improve the material removal rate and cutting velocity whereas higher the wire diameter increase the surface roughness for all the three workpiece material.

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